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as yet, although dioxane is a good solvent having a dielectric constant 2.5 at 25°. In the present communication, the conductivity of KCl, KBr, KNO₃, KBrO₃, KIO₃, K₂SO₄, NaCl, NaBr, NaNO₃, NaBrO₃, NaIO₃ and Na₂SO₄ at 10, 20 and 30 wt % of dioxane and at 30, 35, 40 and 45° ± 0.1°, have been studied. The study gives information regarding the ion-solvent interactions from the mobilities and Walden product of the ions in the solvent. Assumption of Stoke⁸ relating Walden product $\Lambda^\circ \eta$, with the radii of the anions has been employed to estimate the single ion mobilities and ionic Walden product.

Conductivity of Electrolytes in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at different Temperatures

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Experimental

The salts and dioxane used were of E. Merck (extra pure) quality. Preparation of the solvents, solutions and conductance measurements were the same as described earlier³. The conductance measured was accurate up to ± 2 in 1000. The concentration range for uniunivalent salts from 0.01 to 0.001 and for univalent salts from 0.02 to 0.002 mol dm⁻³.

A substantial body of data on the conductances of ions in many aquoorganic solvents, like propylene carbonate, trifluoroethanol, sulpholane, DMSO, DMF and acetone *etc.*¹ have recently been reported. But no study on the conductance of electrolytes in dioxane-water mixtures is reported

Results and Discussion

The Debye-Hückel-Onsager conductance equation is found to be valid as the plot of Λ vs $C^{1/2}$ is linear and the theoretical slope, $(A+B\Lambda^\circ)$ differs from that of the observed one by only 2%. The Λ° values has been obtained from the extra-polated

TABLE 1—IONIC WALDEN PRODUCT ($\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$)/ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ P}$

Temp. °C	Wt % dioxane anion when paired with K ⁺	Anion when paired with K ⁺			Anion when paired with Na ⁺			
		10	20	30	10	20	30	
30	Cl ⁻	0.65	0.63	0.63	Cl ⁻	0.63	0.63	0.63
35		0.63	0.65	0.62		0.61	0.63	0.63
40		0.66	0.65	0.64		0.63	0.63	0.63
45		0.66	0.64	0.65		0.61	0.63	0.63
30		Br ⁻	0.60	0.58		0.59	Br ⁻	0.57
35	0.58		0.59	0.58	0.56	0.56		0.58
40	0.62		0.61	0.59	0.56	0.58		0.58
45	0.59		0.59	0.60	0.56	0.55		0.57
30	NO ₃ ⁻		0.56	0.53	0.54	NO ₃ ⁻		0.53
35		0.53	0.56	0.53	0.50		0.53	0.54
40		0.56	0.56	0.54	0.52		0.51	0.53
45		0.55	0.54	0.55	0.52		0.50	0.52
30		BrO ₃ ⁻	0.47	0.44	0.45		BrO ₃ ⁻	0.42
35	0.45		0.46	0.40	0.43	0.42		0.44
40	0.49		0.49	0.44	0.42	0.44		0.43
45	0.46		0.44	0.45	0.43	0.41		0.42
30	IO ₃ ⁻		0.57	0.54	0.55	IO ₃ ⁻		0.53
35		0.55	0.55	0.53	0.52		0.53	0.54
40		0.55	0.59	0.55	0.52		0.54	0.54
45		0.56	0.54	0.55	0.53		0.52	0.53
30		SO ₄ ²⁻	0.84	0.80	0.67		SO ₄ ²⁻	0.81
35	0.81		0.82	0.78	0.80	0.78		0.66
40	0.83		0.81	0.79	0.79	0.77		0.78
45	0.83		0.80	0.80	0.80	0.77		0.78
30	K ⁺		0.70	0.71	0.70	Na ⁺		0.62
35		0.71	0.69	0.70	0.63		0.62	0.60
40		0.69	0.69	0.70	0.62		0.61	0.60
45		0.70	0.71	0.69	0.62		0.61	0.61

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values at zero concentration. Λ° has also been obtained by Fuoss and Kraus's and Shedlovsky's methods⁴. But the Λ° values are almost the same. The Walden product is almost constant at all temperatures and at all solvent compositions. This constancy is presumably due to the contribution of the positive temperature coefficient of the conductivity with the negative temperature coefficient of the viscosity of the solvent. Hence, it is very difficult to predict about the structure breaking or promoting nature in the solvent, with in the temperature range studied.

The Walden product⁵ may be given by the equation,

$$\Lambda^\circ \eta_0 = (\lambda^\circ_+ + \lambda^\circ_-) \eta_0 = \frac{eF}{6\pi} \left(\frac{1}{r_+} + \frac{1}{r_-} \right)$$

where, e is the electronic charge of the ion, F the force acting on the particle, and r_+ and r_- are the radii of the cation and anion, respectively. Ionic Walden products, $\lambda^\circ_+ \eta_0$ and $\lambda^\circ_- \eta_0$ for the individual ions and hence the single ion mobilities were, therefore, estimated by plotting $\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$ vs the inverse of the radii of the anions⁶. Linear relations were found to exist at all solvent compositions and at all temperatures. By extrapolating the straight line to $1/r_- = 0$, $\lambda^\circ_+ \eta_0$ for K^+ and Na^+ were estimated. Then on subtracting these values from $\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$, the values of $\lambda^\circ_- \eta_0$ for Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , BrO_3^- , IO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} were evaluated (Table 1). It is evident that the values of $\lambda^\circ_- \eta_0$ of the same anions are different when paired with K^+ and Na^+ . This indicates that the spheres of solvation of Na^+ and K^+ are not equally affected.

TABLE 2—Ionic Mobilities λ° - Ω^{-1} cm² (AT 35° ONLY)

(K ⁺)			(Na ⁺)				
Cl ⁻	73.11	61.65	53.57	Cl ⁻	68.78	60.65	52.57
Br ⁻	67.31	57.73	49.32	Br ⁻	64.40	54.80	48.34
NO ₃ ⁻	61.51	54.80	45.07	NO ₃ ⁻	57.53	51.84	44.92
BrO ₃ ⁻	50.74	54.10	34.02	BrO ₃ ⁻	48.33	41.09	33.42
IO ₃ ⁻	62.01	53.82	45.07	IO ₃ ⁻	59.84	51.86	44.92
SO ₄ ²⁻	93.21	80.24	66.33	SO ₄ ²⁻	92.06	76.32	56.13
K ₂ ⁺	80.05	67.52	60.38	Na ⁺	72.50	60.67	51.02

K⁺ = 74.93 and Na⁺ = 51.52 at 25° (Ref. 7).

Then, on dividing the respective ionic Walden products by the viscosity of the solvent, mobility of each ion was estimated. Only the data at 35° are given for illustration. Table 2 shows that the limiting equivalent conductances of all the anions have greater magnitude when paired with K⁺ and less in case of Na⁺. The lesser mobilities may be interpreted as a measure of ion-solvent interaction. Table 2, therefore, suggests that following order of ion-solvent interaction exists in dioxane-water mixtures: BrO₃⁻ > NO₃⁻ > IO₃⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻ > SO₄²⁻ and Na⁺ > K⁺.

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BF₃-catalysed Beckmann Rearrangement of Steroidal unsaturated Ketoximes

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BF₃-catalysed Beckmann rearrangement of α,β -unsaturated steroidal ketoxime is reported to afford an unusual product in addition to usual amide¹. This together with our earlier studies^{2,3} prompted us to undertake the Beckmann rearrangement of 3 β -chlorocholest-5-en-7-one oxime (1), its 3 β -acetoxy analogue (2) and cholesta-3,5-dien-7-one oxime (3). Contrary to our expectation, the reaction followed the usual course and afforded lactams and in some cases their N-acyl derivatives.

The oxime (1) on treatment with BF₃-etherate in acetic anhydride afforded 3 β -chloro-7 α -aza-B-homocholest-5-en-7-one (4) and 7 α -aza B-homocholesta-3,5-dien-7-one (5). On similar treatment, the oximes 2 and 3 gave the corresponding lactams (7 and 5) and the N-acyl derivatives (6 and 8), respectively. The structures of these compounds were established on